

The Oscillator Propagator, Newton's Law and Schrodinger Equation

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The oscillator propagator $\exp(i \text{Action}) = Q(t) \exp[i \frac{m\omega}{2} \{ \cos(\omega t)/\sin(\omega t) (XX + YY) - 2XY / \sin(\omega t) \}] = Q(t) \exp(i \frac{-m}{2} \frac{dA}{dt} / A (XX + YY) - \frac{m\omega}{2} \frac{2XY}{A})$ (where $XA(t)$ is a classical solution with X as amplitude) is a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. Inserting the form with $A(t)$ into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation yields Newton's second law (with two other terms which cancel) i.e. $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} = -k A(t)$. Newton's second law may be multiplied by dA/dt and integrated, yielding the well-known conservation of energy equation: $\text{Energy} = XX \frac{dA}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} \frac{m}{2} + \frac{k}{2} XX AA$. Thus, the two are equivalent as is known from classical mechanics.

One may consider solving the time dependent Schrodinger equation in a different manner, namely postulating a separable solution of the form: $\exp(-i C t) H(x)$. Substituting into the oscillator Schrodinger equation yields $C = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + .5 k x x W$. Mathematically, this equation may be solved, but only a discrete set of C values yield solutions, namely $C = .5 \omega(n+.5)$ with corresponding $W_n(x)$. We argue that this mathematical equation may be linked to a physical one, namely the conservation of energy equation if C is associated with energy. In such a case, one must associate $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ with classical kinetic energy at a x .

At this point, we suggest one must establish a physical interpretation for $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ if W . We argue that X in $\exp(i \text{Action})$ is an amplitude. Allowing all values of X (e.g. $-1/2m \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dX}$) means allowing all amplitudes for a particular spring. Thus it seems that one is considering a fluctuating amplitude picture in which these fluctuations can yield an average energy associated with a particular E_n . This average equation follows classical mechanics in terms of average $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$.

Oscillator Propagator

The classical equation for an oscillator is: $\frac{m}{2} \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} + .5k x x = E$ which may be written in terms of Newton's law as: $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} = -k x$. Given the nature of this equation, one may find the solution $X \sin(\omega t)$ with $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$, where X is an amplitude. Different X values mean different amplitudes and different overall energies $.5kXX$.

The recipe for the propagator is: $Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \int_{(0,t)} L$ where L is the Lagrangian. Following (1), we write:

$$x(t) = X \frac{A(T_f - t)}{A(T_f - T_i)} + Y \frac{A(t - T_i)}{A(T_f - T_i)} \text{ with } T_i = 0 \text{ and } T_f = T \quad ((1))$$

Calculating the propagator yields: $Q(t) \exp[i \{ \frac{m}{2} \{ \cos(\omega t)/\sin(\omega t) (XX + YY) \} - [\frac{m\omega}{2}] \frac{2XY}{\sin(\omega t)} \}] \quad ((2))$

This may be rewritten as:

$$K = Q(t) \exp(i \{-\frac{1}{2} m \frac{dA}{dt} / A (XX + YY)\} - 2(mw/2)XY/A) \quad ((3))$$

where $X_A(t)$ is the classical solution of Newton's second law. Here X is an amplitude, but in the propagator it is treated as a variable. This seems to imply that any value of X may be used, i.e. any amplitude of a given spring. Thus, having ((3)) be a solution of the time dependent Schrodinger equation with $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ as a term suggests different amplitudes are associated with this equation. In other words, it seems that one is considering a certain class of fluctuations i.e. amplitude fluctuations.

By inserting ((3)) into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and equating real coefficients of XX one obtains Newton's second law, as two unrelated terms cancel i.e.

$$I \frac{d}{dt} K = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} K + .5 k x x K \quad ((4))$$

Here we use X and x interchangeably. ((4)) becomes:

$$-1/2 m \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{dA}{dt} / A] = 1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} K + .5k x x K$$

$$-1/2 m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} = k A \quad \text{because } -\frac{1}{2} m (-\frac{dA}{dt} / [AA]) \text{ cancels with } -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} K \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the Schrodinger equation for the oscillator is really Newton's second law. Given that this may be multiplied by dA/dt and integrated means it may be converted into a conservation of energy equation:

$$E/XX = 1/2m \frac{dA}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} + k/2 AA \quad \text{where } X \text{ is the amplitude} \quad ((6))$$

Next, consider the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and postulate a solution of the form $\exp(-iCt) W(x)$ i.e. a separable solution. This leads to:

$$CW = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + k/2 W \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is a mathematical differential equation which has solutions for specific values of C namely $w(n+.5)$ where $w = \sqrt{k/m}$ and corresponding $W_n(x)$. The $W_n(x)$ form a mathematical basis. Given the forms of ((6)) and ((7)), if one chooses $C=E$, (i.e. chooses a particular amplitude X) then $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ must be identical to classical kinetic energy at x . The question becomes: Is there a physical interpretation for W or is it simply a mathematical function? In equation ((6)), one follows a classical particle at each time i.e. $x = X_A(t)$. X is a specific amplitude for a given energy. ((7)) is completely different. Even though there is a fixed energy E_n , $x=X$ takes on any value. Thus, one has all different amplitudes X creating some kind of "average" state with energy E_n . In this picture, ((7)) represents a fluctuating system which on average yields average classical values.

In particular, the fluctuating piece of the Schrodinger equation is $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ which is related to the classical result $-\frac{1}{2} m (-\frac{dA}{dt} A/dt / [AA])$ in the oscillator case, where $X_A(t)$ is the classical trajectory.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the propagator $K = Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$ which appears to be a strictly classical object, is the solution to a differential equation namely the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. For the oscillator case, $K = Q(t) \exp(i \{ -m/2dA/dt / A (XX+YY) - 2(mw/2)XY/A \})$. Inserting K into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and equating coefficients of XX yields Newton's second law. It is interesting to note that $XA(t)$ is the classical Newton's law solution, so X (or Y if you wish) is the amplitude. Both the propagator and the Schrodinger equation allow for all X values, so it seems all amplitudes are being considered. By equating coefficients of XX , XX cancel in the Schrodinger equation, but the presence of $-1/2m d/dx d/dx (x=X)$ implies that different amplitude values are allowed.

Integrating Newton's law gives the expected conservation of energy equation $E = m/2 XX dA/dt + k/2 XX AA$. One may postulate a solution $\exp(-iCt)W(x)$ to the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. This leads to a differential equation with solutions for only some C values namely $w(n+0.5)$ with corresponding $Wn(x)$ which form a complete basis. Thus, the time-dependent oscillator may also be converted into an energy conservation equation, with the fluctuation term $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx$ representing average kinetic energy at x . (When inserting the propagator, written in terms of dA/dt and A , the kinetic energy fluctuation term canceled out, leaving Newton's second law.)

Thus, we argue that the time-dependent Schrodinger equation appears to be a special kind of fluctuation equation closely linked to the classical solution. In the oscillator case, one sees that $\exp(i m/2 dA/dt / A XX)$ inserted into the DE yields Newton's second law which is also equivalent to a conservation of energy equation.

References

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